

Condensation of Succinyl Chloride with Phenols : Synthesis of 1 : 4-Diketones

D. Chakravarti, Nripendra Kumar Roy, Anjali Chakravarti and Usha Sarkar

Succinyl chloride has been condensed with phenols in presence of $AlCl_3$ forming aryloxy esters, which have been submitted to double Fries' rearrangement forming 1:4-diketones.

In earlier papers Chakravarti and his co-workers^{1,2} have shown that glutaryl chloride and adipyl chloride when condensed with free phenols in presence of aluminium chloride in the presence of a solvent e.g., nitrobenzene yield mainly *p*-hydroxyketo-acids in good yield, along with the diketones.

In the present communication, the authors have described the condensation of succinyl chloride with phenols under identical conditions. It is, however, remarkable that phenol and cresols condense with succinyl chloride in the presence of aluminium chloride forming aryloxy esters and not diketones or keto carboxylic acids as in the condensation with glutaryl chloride and adipyl chloride. *p*-Substituted phenols, e.g., *p*-cresol, *p*-chlorophenol, 4-chloro-*m*-cresol form aryloxy esters when condensed with succinyl chloride, glutaryl chloride and adipyl chloride. The condensation of *p*-bromophenol, chloroxylenol, eugenol, α -naphthol, 4-chloro-1-naphthol with succinyl chloride also leads to the formation of aryloxy esters(I). Some of the esters obtained by the condensation of succinyl chloride with the phenols have been submitted to double Fries' rearrange-

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ment in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride yielding crystalline 1:4-diketones of the type (II) in good yield.

The aryloxy ester from 4-chloro-1-naphthol when submitted to Fries' rearrangement forms diketone which has the probable structure (III).

Thomas Shamma and Fernelius¹ also reported that succinic acid reacts with *p*-cresol in presence of phosphorous oxychloride yielding *p*-cresyl succinate which was submitted to the double Fries' rearrangement with aluminium chloride in presence of carbon disulphide and chlorobenzene yielding diketone.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diphenyl Succinate—Method A. A solution of freshly distilled phenol (2.4 g.) in nitrobenzene (20 ml.) was cooled in a three-necked flask equipped with stirrer, dropping funnel and a gas out-let tube. Aluminium chloride (7.5 g.) was added and the solution was cooled to 0-5°. A solution of succinyl chloride (3.9 g.) in nitrobenzene (10 ml.) was added during 30 min. After keeping at room temperature for 18 hr. it was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid, and nitrobenzene removed by steam distillation. The product was crystallised from dil. alcohol as needles. m.p. 124° (yield, 2 gm.)

Method B. Succinic acid (11 g.) and phenol (20 g.) in a flask equipped with thermometer and a reflux condenser protected by a guard tube was heated for 2-3 hr. at 115-120° with the addition of phosphorous oxychloride (10 g.) dropwise. The cold reaction mixture was poured into ice. Crystals separating were filtered, dried and crystallised from dilute ethanol, and had m.p. 124°.

Method C. When a solution of succinyl chloride and phenol was heated in a water bath for 3 hr., it gave an ester. m.p. 125° (Found: C, 71.57, H, 5.60. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₄O₄: C, 71.11, H, 5.18%).

All the esters of succinic acids were prepared by similar methods as described for diphenyl succinate.

The products of condensation of phenols and substituted phenols with succinic acid are described in Table I.

CONDENSATION OF SUCCINYL CHLORIDE WITH PHENOLS:

TABLE I

Phenols and substituted phenols.	Condensation products	Formula	m.p.	Analysis	
				Required:	Found:
1. <i>o</i> -cresol	Di-(<i>o</i> -toluyl) succinate (I, R=CH ₃ , R ₂ =R ₃ =H)	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄	b.p. 240°/5mm ⁴		
2. <i>m</i> -cresol	Di-(<i>m</i> -toluyl) succinate (I, R ₁ =CH ₃ , R ₂ =R ₃ =H)	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄	m.p. 60° ⁴		
3. 4-chloro- <i>m</i> -cresol	Di-(4-chloro-3-methyl phenyl) succinate (I, R ₂ =Cl, R ₁ =CH ₃ , R ₃ =H)	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ Cl ₂	m.p. 91°	C, 58.85 H, 4.36	C, 58.75 H, 4.32
4. <i>o</i> -chlorophenol	Di-(<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl) succinate (I, R=Cl, R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H)	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ Cl ₂	m.p. 90°	C, 56.63 H, 3.54	C, 56.65 H, 3.42
5. <i>p</i> -chlorophenol	Di-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl) succinate (I, R=Cl, R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H)	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ Cl ₂	m.p. 105°	C, 56.63 H, 3.54	C, 56.52 H, 3.24
6. <i>p</i> -cresol	Di-(<i>p</i> -toluyl) succinate (I, R ₂ =CH ₃ , R ₁ =R ₃ =H)	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄	m.p. 121°	C, 72.48 H, 6.04	C, 72.12 H, 6.14
7. <i>p</i> -bromophenol	Di-(<i>p</i> -bromophenyl) succinate. (I, R ₂ =Br, R ₁ =R ₃ =H)	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ Br ₂	m.p. 112°	C, 44.86 H, 2.80	C, 44.75 H, 2.83
8. eugenol	Di-(4-allyl-2-methoxy phenyl) succinate. (I, R=OCH ₃ , R ₂ =CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ , (R ₁ =R ₃ =H)	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₈	m.p. 87°	C, 70.24 H, 6.34	C, 70.13 H, 5.92
9. Cl-xyleneol	Di-(4-chloro-3,5-dimethyl phenyl) succinate. (I, R ₂ =Cl, R ₁ =R ₃ =CH ₃ , R=H)	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ Cl ₂	m.p. 120°	C, 60.75 H, 5.06	C, 60.64 H, 4.99
10. α -naphthol	Di-(α -naphthyl) succinate	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₄	m.p. 160°	C, 77.84 H, 4.86	C, 77.67 H, 4.87
11. 4-chloro-1-naphthol.	Di-(4-chloro-1-naphthyl) succinate	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ O ₄	m.p. 140°	C, 65.60 H, 3.64	C, 65.45 H, 3.57

Synthesis of 1, 4-Diketones by Double Fries' Rearrangement. Synthesis of Bis (2-hydroxy-5-chloro phenyl) 1, 4-butanedione.—Di-*p*-chlorophenylsuccinate (3 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (3 g.) were placed in a flask equipped with thermometer and air condenser fitted with a calcium chloride guard tube. The flask with the contents were heated to 130—140° for 3-4 hr. After the reaction was completed it was allowed to cool, decomposed by ice and conc. HCl and was kept overnight. The decomposed product was then extracted with ether. The brownish product obtained after removal of ether was dissolved in 5% alkali solution. The alkali solution on acidification gave crystalline product (m.p. 180°). It was crystallised from dilute alcohol and had m.p. 182°. (Found: C, 56.60, H, 3.68; C₁₆H₁₂O₄Cl₂ requires C, 56.63, H, 3.54%). It gives violet colouration with FeCl₃ solution. Di-D.N.P. m.p. 210° (Found; N, 16.59; C₂₀H₂₀O₄Cl₂N₂ requires N, 16.02%.)

Dioxime, m.p. 175° (Found: N, 7.0; C₁₆H₁₄O₄Cl₂N₂ requires N, 7.59%).

The other diketones, obtained by Fries' rearrangement with anhydrous $AlCl_3$, are described in Table II.

TABLE II

Diaryl esters	Rearrangement products -1,4-Butane-dione	Formula	Analysis		Derivative.
			Required	Found	
1. Di-(<i>p</i> -toluyl) succinate	Bis (2-hydroxy-5 methyl phenyl- $C_{10}H_{10}O_4$ (II, $R_2=CH_3$, $R=R_1=R_3=H$) m.p. 189°. reported m.p. 187°. Fries and Bartens <i>Ann.</i> 1924, 422, 270	$C_{18}H_{18}O_4$	C, 72.48 H, 6.04	C, 72.32 H, 6.25	Di-D.N.P. m.p. 239°. Found: N, 16.3; $C_{30}H_{26}O_{10}N_8$ requires N, 17.0. Di-Oxime. m.p. 269° Found: N, 7.80; $C_{18}H_{20}O_4N_8$ requires N, 8.53
2. Di-(<i>p</i> -bromo-phenyl) succinate)	Bis (2-hydroxy 5-bromophenyl- (II, $R_2=Br$, $R=R_1$ $=R_3=H$) m.p. 180°.	$C_{16}H_{12}O_4Br_2$	C, 44.86 H, 2.80	C, 44.45 H, 2.63	Di-D.N.P. m.p. 250° Found: N, 13.75; $C_{28}H_{20}N_8O_{10}Br_2$ re- quires N, 14.21%
3. Di (4-chloro-3-methyl phenyl)- succinate	Bis (2-hydroxy 5-chloro, 4-methyl phenyl) (II, $R_2=Cl$, $R_1=CH_3$; $R=R_3$ $=H$) m.p. 194°.	$C_{18}H_{16}O_4Cl_2$	C, 58.85 H, 4.36	C, 58.99 H, 4.01	Di-D.N.P. m.p. 250° Found: N, 15.4; $C_{30}H_{24}N_8O_{10}Cl_2$ re- quires N, 15.40%
4. Di-(4-chloro-3,5 dimethyl phenyl) succinate	Bis (2 hydroxy-4:6 dimethyl, 5-chloro- phenyl- (II, $R_2=Cl$, $R_1=R_3=CH_3$, $R=H$) m.p. 250°.	$C_{20}H_{20}O_4Cl_2$	C, 60.75 H, 5.06	C, 60.44 H, 5.69	Di-D. N. P. m.p. 220° Found: N, 14.0; $C_{32}H_{28}O_{10}N_8Cl_2$ requires N, 14.83%
5. Di (4-chloro-1-naphthyl) succinate	Bis (2 hydroxy 7-chloro- naphthyl) (III)- m.p. 200°.	$C_{24}H_{18}O_4Cl_2$	C, 65.60 H, 3.64	C, 65.15 H, 3.57	Di-D.N.P., m.p. 240° Found: N, 13.95; $C_{26}H_{24}O_{10}N_8Cl_2$ requires N, 14.01%

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA-9.

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